

SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE ANTHROPOLOGICAL CONCEPTS OF ABU RAIKHAN BERUNI

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Abstract. Actualizing the problem of educating the younger generation of Uzbekistan, the author refers to the specifics of social, anthropological knowledge on the example of Beruni's views. The works and statements of the philosopher about the nature of man and the ethnic diversity of peoples are considered. The value of humanistic ideas for the formation of social foundations, the worldview of the individual and national self-consciousness is emphasized.

Keywords: Beruni, anthropological concept, society, man, social cognition.

INTRODUCTION

Appeal to the issues of spirituality is dictated by the strategic need to educate qualified personnel in Uzbekistan, which are designed to ensure the "phased and sustainable development of the country" [1]. Talented youth at all times were drawn to the sages, we will also turn to Abu Rayhan al-Beruni and his thoughts on the natural foundations of human existence in society.

MAIN PART

Al-Beruni is recognized in the history of science as the founder of a new branch of science about measuring the terrain and the surface of the earth - geodesy. In the field of mineralogy, the scientist for the first time measured the specific gravity of solids and liquids using his own device and, on the basis of this, proposed a classification of minerals, developed a theory of their origin and paragenetic information.

Knowing Arabic, Persian, Greek, Syriac, as well as Sanskrit, al-Beruni contributed to the development of principles for translating natural scientific terminology from one language to another.

The American historian George Sarton said the following about this outstanding encyclopedic scientist: "The history of astronomy and mathematics, astrology and geography, anthropology and ethnography, archeology and philosophy, botany and mineralogy would be orphaned without his great name."

Our great ancestor believed that everything in nature exists and changes according to the laws of nature itself, and these laws can be comprehended only with the help of science. His works devoted to mathematics and astronomy were

of great practical importance for the economic life of Khorezm, including for irrigated agriculture and trade exchange.

In the very first work, *The Chronology of Ancient Peoples*, the genius collected and described all the calendar systems known in his time, used by various peoples of the world. Astronomical studies are given by him in the "Book of Interpretation of the Basic Principles of Astronomy" and other scientific works.

In the work "India", al-Beruni gave a detailed description of the life, culture and science of the Indians, outlined their religious and philosophical systems. The transcription system he created on the basis of Arabic script in many respects anticipated the modern system of rendering Indian words in Urdu.

In the work "Saidana" ("Pharmacognosy"), the great thinker describes in detail more than a thousand medicinal, 150 ordinary plants and more than a hundred animals. The scientist, having collected information in Arabic, Greek, Indian, Persian, Sogdian and other languages about 4 thousand species of plants, animals, minerals and substances derived from them, made a huge contribution to streamlining the terms of the pharmaceutical business.

About human nature

We find basic information about Beruni's views on man and society in his works "India", "Osor-ul-bokiya", in mathematical and astronomical treatises [2]. The anthropological researches of the scientist are mostly connected with the study of religions, often with geography. Statements about ethics and human destiny are found in many scientific works of the scientist, which is due to the multidimensionality of the essential nature of man, in which he appears at the same time:

- creation of God,
- natural organism,
- a structural element of society [3].

In the dedication to the Emir of Gurgenj, with which Beruni precedes the "Chronology of ancient peoples ("Osor-ul-bokia"), the author touches on the foundations of the formation of public institutions: "... the emergence of customs and religions, the history and formation of some nations ... either from other people's words, or according to their own observations and conclusions ... fix it on paper ... so that it is a new service, ... the memory of which will remain a legacy to posterity, while centuries pass and generations pass" [4]. In social cognition, the thinker turns to the analysis of determinant factors that influence

the final choice of the direction of peoples' development, mainly, the material foundations of being and ways of producing material goods [5]. When evaluating social phenomena, Beruni refers to the categories of good and evil, justice, moral values, calls on people to "cleanse their souls from bad properties", and from the reasons that make them blind "to the truth":

- lust for power,
- passions and predilections,
- ingrained habits,
- competitive spirit.

The latter property is especially cultivated in modern society, and one should think about its manipulative nature.

About political correctness

Dedicated to the chronology of peoples, the work of al-Beruni "Monuments of Past Generations" is actually a historical and ethnographic study, which is based on:

- written sources,
- oral tradition,
- author's observations.

The philosopher's attitude to the problem of ethnic and religious diversity is connected with the question of the "beginning of beginnings", i.e. about the beginning of human history, for the resolution of which the author cites the words of the prophet: "Every newborn is born the way [God] created him, and then his parents make him a Jew, a Christian or a magician" [4]. The great scientist and prominent political figure of his era, an Iranian who knew his native culture deeply, but at the same time a Muslim who wrote his works in Arabic and perfectly understood the Arab tradition, al-Beruni existed all his life at the intersection of various cultural worlds, which required the creator treatise on the implementation of new mental attitudes:

1. about the unity of human nature,
2. about the identity of the cultures of all (even small) regions.

The first setting is based on the fact that "there is a law of causality in nature, the same causes give rise to the same consequences", and the second one (about the identity of cultures) is based on the fact that "due to the actions of various forces, changes are constantly taking place in nature" [4]. The scientific method, which al-Beruni equally applied in natural science and in historical and ethnographic works, allowed him to conclude: different peoples live in different

conditions, they have completely different customs and traditions, this must be taken for granted, avoiding categorical value judgments [6].

CONCLUSION

The value of the humanistic ideas of Abu Rayhan al-Beruni for modern society lies in the fact that he managed to maintain national identity in the conditions of forced emigration. Having devoted most of his life to serving at the court of the Gaznevid sultans, he remained a true son of Khorezm and gave the Uzbek people a rich pedagogical heritage.

The link connecting national thinking with universal philosophy is the worldview of each member of society, the formation of which should become one of the main tasks of modern pedagogy [7], along with stimulating the social activity of society and the formation of democratic institutions.

References:

1. Karimov, I.A. (2009). Ensuring the gradual and sustainable development of our country is our main village. -T. 17. - Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2009. - p. 137.
2. Umarova R. Some aspects of the relationship between nature, man and society in the views of Abu Ali Ibn Sino and Abu Rayhan Beruni // Theoretical & Applied Science. – 2015. – no. 10. - S. 127-129.
3. Colin K. Information anthropology: A new concept of knowledge of human nature // Researcher. European Journal of Humanities & Social Sciences. - 2019. - Vol. 2. - No. 3. - S. 85-115.
4. Reykhan B. A. Monuments of past generations, translated by MA Salier // Selected Works. - T. 1.
5. Ryabokon, N.V. Fundamentals of scientific research methodology: lectures [Electronic resource] // Minsk: MIU, 2016. – http://media.miu.by/files/store/lecture/Riabokon_OMNI_2016.pdf
6. Gritsyuk E. Yu. The image of the “other”: the Persians in al-Biruni’s “Monuments of Past Generations” // Imagines mundi: Almanac of the Studies of World History of the 16th–20th centuries, No. 5. Intellectual History. Issue. 3. - 2008. - S. 254-262.
7. Ikramov R. A., Khozhiev R. B. U. Education of a harmoniously developed generation is a priority of the state youth policy. Vestnik nauki i obrazovaniya. – 2020. – no. 14-1(92).

